

National-Local Dissonance and Exacerbated Vulnerabilities: COVID-19 and PH Governmental Response

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Abstract. The chasm between good and bad governance widens during times of prolonged crisis. The COVID-19 pandemic proved how well-governed countries could climb out of the initial waves of infection while others struggled or failed to provide substantial efforts to curb the disease. Vulnerable groups, such as women, youth, children, the elderly, poor households, as well as communities that depend on the informal economy, with limited access to social and health services, are made even more vulnerable because of the uncertainties brought by the pandemic. Even non-traditional vulnerable groups, such as migrant workers and locally stranded individuals have become vulnerable due to this unprecedented health crisis. This article attempts to examine how the disease has affected the lives of ordinary Filipinos, as they confronted not only an invisible enemy but also state-imposed COVID-19 measures that inadvertently left them in an even more precarious state. The authors argue that state-imposed COVID-19 measures increased the risk of already vulnerable groups rather than protect them. In doing so, the article attempts to identify the effects of the pandemic and corresponding government responses to (1) the plight of locally stranded individuals and (2) community quarantines.

Keywords: emerging vulnerable sectors, COVID-19, Philippines

Before the onset of COVID-19, the Philippines enjoyed positive projections of economic growth between 6.1% in 2020 and 6.2% in 2021 by the World Bank. Based on the Philippine Statistics Authority's (PSA) January 2020 Labor Force Survey, employment rate was estimated at 94.7% (PSA, 2020) and, conversely, the World Bank saw the country's poverty incidence declining from 20.8% toward the end of 2019 to 18.7% in 2021 (De Vera, 2019). Then President Rodrigo Duterte was enjoying a record-high satisfaction rate from the Social Weather Stations (SWS)

survey in January 2020, despite criticisms of human rights violations against his administration, his war on drugs, and continuous assault on the media.

By mid-2020, the Philippines had a 16.5% retraction of the economy coupled with a recession which has not happened in 29 years (*Al Jazeera*, 2020). By the second quarter of 2020 at the height of the enhanced community quarantine (ECQ), unemployment also hit a record high of 17.7 % (De Vera, 2020). Within the same year, while the Philippine government struggled to respond to the pandemic, Congress passed the Anti-Terrorism Act of 2020, media giant ABS-CBN was ordered to shut down, and journalist Maria Ressa was convicted for a cyber libel case. The political and economic climate then, along with the continuous surge of COVID-19 cases and the uncertainty of vaccine availability, contributed to the overall sentiment about the Duterte administration's response to the pandemic being overly securitized and disconnected from the more pressing need of the population, particularly those who are marginalized and vulnerable.

The vulnerabilities of certain sectors, such as women, children and the youth, elderly, informal workers, migrant workers, and poor households, were exacerbated by a securitized frame of responding to the crisis that saw more beefed-up policies concerning threats to national security and attacks on what were perceived to be weaknesses in government responses meant to facilitate the provision of various social services to those in need.

Vulnerable Sectors

Vulnerable populations could refer to individuals whose risks are greater than the dominant population in physical, social, and economic status (Rukmana, 2014). Vulnerable populations or sectors include children, pregnant women, households with PWDs, indigenous peoples, homeless street families, and families in need of special protection (National Economic and Development Authority, 2017). Women and children often have more intensified vulnerability due to the inherent marginalization and inequality they face regularly (Cader & Perera, 2011). However, many of these groups' existing vulnerabilities have been exacerbated by their exposure to the unprecedented risks presented by COVID-19.

Migrant workers, for example, are considered a vulnerable population, owing to their exposure to a specific variety of risks, including their low-income status and the precarity of their jobs (Molenaar & Van Praag, 2022). At the height of the pandemic, the plight of migrant workers was made worse due to heightened uncertainty and insecurity. Migrant workers were either stranded or displaced in their countries of work. Many others were left unprotected without a visa or valid working papers, aggravating their situation and making it difficult for their governments to repatriate them to their home countries.

Aside from migrant workers, another group whose vulnerability was exacerbated due to government policies were individuals working in Metro Manila at the time of the pandemic and were stranded in various areas in the region with limited or zero access to basic needs. They were labeled as locally stranded individuals or LSIs. While the concept of individuals being stranded during the pandemic was not isolated in the Philippines, the term itself can be considered unique. Mostly construction and factory workers and vendors, these LSIs originated from the provinces and, at the time of the COVID outbreak, had been working in Metro Manila to provide for their families back

in their hometowns. Their vulnerability is compounded by the limitations imposed on their mobility going to and from their places of work. For LSIs whose places of work were forced shut, they were left with no jobs to pay for basic needs and, thus, were left to fend for themselves, while they waited for transportation that would shuttle them back to their provinces. For others, waiting for help turned for the worse. For instance, a housemaid waited for a bus that would take her back to her home province, but she was stranded for days and was later found dead in a footbridge along Pasay City (Regan, 2020). Help was extended to overseas Filipino workers (OFWs), especially in repatriation, but LSIs felt abandoned by the government for not receiving the same level of attention as stranded OFWs (Talabong, 2020a).

Significance of the Study

This study aims to contribute to the understanding of the effects of disasters and calamities of catastrophic proportions, as nuanced by the shifts in the responsibilities of governmental actors at the national and local level and in the multiplier effect on risks to vulnerable and emerging vulnerable sectors. Bringing the intersection of this new layer of responsibilities to governmental actors and risks to vulnerable sectors will ultimately require an increase in the coordinative capacity of national and local government.

Review of the Literature

Pandemic Responses

The Philippine government introduced several policies to respond to COVID-19. Perhaps the most contentious policies would be those signifying Duterte's highly securitized frame of response. One of the highly employed policies at the start of the pandemic was to put specific areas in lockdowns. Depending on the severity or surge of COVID-19 cases at a given time, the lockdowns came in waves and often corresponded with either total or partial community quarantine. Once an area was put under quarantine, residents became subject to mobility restrictions, violations of which were met with corresponding sanctions. These lockdowns adversely affected informal workers, the urban poor, and women (Hecita et al., 2023). Informal workers, for one, depend on being able to move for their daily livelihood and other sources of income.

Government restrictions on mobility came with guidelines concerning social distancing, and interpretations appeared to vary, depending on the implementation of the local government unit. Either way, both policies inadvertently targeted informal communities. Collantes (2021) looked closely into the stringent measures applied to the mobility of people in informal communities, and how these measures were detrimental to their already precarious living conditions. For Sitio San Roque, the subject of Collantes' case study, the risks to the well-being of those in informal communities ranged from being more exposed to the virus, to not having good access to basic hygiene necessities, clean water, sewage, or even infrastructure that could facilitate access to these (Collantes, 2021). Being quarantined under a total lockdown without access to services that could protect them from the virus, coupled with social distancing made impractical due to their limited or overcrowded space, the informal communities' vulnerability was unnecessarily heightened.

In Southeast Asia, pandemic responses likewise involved variations in mobility restrictions and corresponding social safety net policies. Vietnam's case is interesting, as it is described as successful in containment and mitigation. The response included isolation measures, quarantine, and temporary lockdown of a specific community during the first wave of identified COVID-19 infections (Hartley et al., 2021). Like the Philippines, Vietnam also offered financial assistance to its impacted population. It implemented fiscal and monetary policies to support affected industries and to cushion the blow of the pandemic and push its economy toward relative stability. But Vietnam's COVID-19 response was heralded as one of the most effective globally. It is included in the list of countries that acted swiftly and decisively to test, trace, and quarantine possible cases, thus preventing the virus from spreading, especially during the first wave of the outbreak (United Nations Vietnam, 2020). This shows how varying impositions of mobility policies and monetary assistance have led economies to differing outcomes, with others having more success in their approach and setting the benchmark for effective pandemic response.

National Policies on COVID-19

The unprecedented fashion with which COVID-19 has swept through the globe significantly affected the lives of everyone, regardless of economic or political background. Different governments struggled to stay on their feet as they recalibrated their policies repeatedly with every surge of positive cases that threatened to collapse their health system and upset their economy.

From the moment the first case of coronavirus in the Philippines was confirmed on 30 January 2020, the government has, through the Office of the President and the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) member agencies, released numerous policies related to the pandemic. Some of these policies cut across themes, such as financial assistance, mobility, education, and quarantine, and involve multiple agencies in terms of sector implementation (Berse et al., 2020).

IATF Policies on COVID-19

Among the first policies released by the Office of the President was Presidential Proclamation No. 929, which placed the Philippines in a state of calamity due to local transmission (Table 1). This declaration came with a lockdown of Luzon Island under Enhanced Community Quarantine between midnight of 17 March to 12 April 2020, the first of many versions of community quarantines imposed in various areas in the country. Putting Luzon under quarantine was met with heavy criticisms from multiple sectors, citing government indifference to what the people needed to feel more secure amid the disease. While the lockdown sought to contain the disease outbreak (Merez, 2020), the chilling effect of restricting movements and suspending public transportation became a concern for many, particularly commuters, workers, and employers (Gregorio, 2020).

Table 1
*Selected National Policies from the Office of the President,
March to July 2020*

Date	Law/Policy	Description
16 March 2020	Presidential Proclamation No. 922	Declaration of state of public health emergency due to local transmission
16 March 2020	Presidential Proclamation No. 929	Declaration of state of calamity in the Philippines due to local transmission. Luzon Island was put on enhanced community quarantine from midnight of 16 March to 12 April 2020.
23 March 2020	Republic Act 11469	Known as the “Bayanihan to Heal as One Act,” this act provides a national policy for COVID-19. It authorizes the president to exercise powers needed to address the pandemic.
29 April 2020	Executive Order No. 112	An executive order imposing enhanced community quarantine in high-risk geographic areas in Luzon and some high-risk areas in Visayas and Mindanao. It also put all low-risk and moderate-risk areas on general community quarantine from 1-15 May 2020.
6 May 2020	Executive Order No. 114	An executive order that institutionalizes the “Balik Probinsya, Bagong Pag-Asa” Program to push for balanced regional development. It promoted development and inclusive growth in the countryside.
27 July 2020	Republic Act 11494	Known as the “Bayanihan Recover as One program”, the law provides economic stimulus and additional protection for COVID-19-affected sectors.

Source. Official Gazette of the Philippines.

Table 2
Inter-Agency Task Force on the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID) Resolutions

Date Issued	Law/Policy	Description
28 January 2020	IATF Resolution No. 1	Creation of guidelines in managing the COVID-19 situation: (1) ensure support to Filipinos in China; (2) ensure transportation plans for voluntary returning Filipinos in Hubei Province; (3) propose temporary restrictions on visa issuance for travelers from Hubei province; and (4) discourage non-essential travels of Filipinos to China.
11 February 2020	IATF Resolution No. 4	Expanded travel ban against entry from and travel to China, Hong Kong, Macau, and Taiwan.
9 March 2020	IATF Resolution No. 10	Adoption of social distancing measures in the National Capital Region (NCR) per the recommendation of the DOH, salient points of which were (1) class suspension in all levels in Metro Manila from 10 until 14 March 2020; (2) temporary prohibition of mass gatherings; and (3) implementation of alternative working arrangements in the private and government sectors.
13 March 2020	IATF Resolution No. 12	Implementation of more stringent social distancing measures in NCR; formation of composite teams by the DOH to ensure contact tracing and containment in the country; approval of Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) protocols on social amelioration; expanding members of the IATF to include the rest of the national agencies, including the Philippines National Police, Armed Forces of the Philippines, Office of the Chief Presidential Legal Counsel, Presidential Communications Operations Office, Philippine Coast Guard, the National Security Adviser, and the Cabinet Secretary.
20 March 2020	IATF Resolution No. 14	Inclusion of the concerns and accommodation of distressed OFWs to guidelines set by the Overseas Workers Welfare Administration (OWWA).
24 March 2020	IATF Resolution No. 15	Release of National Action Plan for COVID-19, including repatriation plans for affected OFWs.

Source. Official Gazette of the Philippines.

The social distancing policies adopted by the IATF through Resolution No. 10 recommended drastic changes that aimed to prevent the cases of COVID-19 from escalating further. Such efforts included recommendations to employers to implement alternative work arrangements in the workplace, suspension of classes and school-

related activities across all levels in Metro Manila and cancellation of sports events (Montemayor, 2020). Such efforts to control the pandemic drew attention to the capacity of the Philippines' education system to adapt to different modes of learning without risking the continuity and quality of education delivered to the students. The sudden shift to an alternative learning mode besides onsite classes proved challenging, as remote learning, whether online, modular, or blended, is not yet fully institutionalized in the country (Berse, 2020).

Theoretical Framework

The extraordinary times that capture the real effect of pandemic period policies on vulnerable groups can be defined in Beasley's (2018) discussion of hazards and risks. There is a distinction between "hazards," which are usually natural catastrophes and "risks" which Beck (1992, as cited in Beasley, 2018) differentiates as "potential catastrophes that humanity has itself created. These, in turn, are rooted in decision-making that has included a sense of acceptability of some risk in exchange for benefits" (Beasley, 2018, p. 5). "[R]isks presume industrial, that is, techno-economic decisions and considerations of utility. ... They differ from pre-industrial natural disasters by their origin in decision-making" (Beck, 1992, p. 98, as cited in Beasley, 2018, p. 5).

This article focuses on the decision-making origin of some pandemic-centric risks and how these have adversely affected vulnerable groups. Beasley (2018) identifies risk factors, sources of dissonance, and dissonance reduction measures by decision-makers that negatively impact the policy-making process. Beasley (2018) focuses on the dissonance aspect of policymaking in risk-activated situations (he uses the "war on terror" to illustrate) and reveals the possible sources, strategies, and impacts on the decision-making process.

This article carries the view that, similarly, in the pandemic decision-making space, the desire to make unwanted consequences "less aversive" increases blame avoidance behavior, resulting in negative impacts, ranging from "poor information search to biased processing, poor group dynamics, a poor survey of objectives, confirmation bias or overconfidence and over-reliance on external expertise" (Beasley, 2018, p. 9). This article argues that the cognitive dissonance in decision making was most felt as national-level directives at the task force level were implemented by local governments that were not used to the resources (or lack thereof), the pace, and the sheer scale of their decision-making scope.

Method

This work is a qualitative study largely undertaken during the pandemic when mobility was limited. The researchers were confined to the following secondary methods of data collection via online search:

1. Review of literature on the role of the state during crisis periods (including various forms of displacement);
2. Local and national government data on government policies during the pandemic; and
3. News reports during the early pandemic (2020-2021).

Data analysis was undertaken through thematic analysis of the documents procured during the period. Two cases are highlighted in this study:

1. Locally stranded individuals (LSIs), *ayuda* (financial aid) and quarantine communities (representing emerging vulnerable groups), and
2. OFWs (representing more traditional groups).

Cases

National Policies and Local Context

The Philippine government's COVID-19 pandemic responses are thematic, with some issues stressed more strongly than others, such as those that concern the movement of people within and across specified zones in the local government, social welfare, and livelihood. Some of these policy responses have received scrutiny from different sectors, not only for lack of clarity on those that overlap like that of "Balik Probinsya, Balik Pag-Asa" and "Hatid Tulong," which confused people who wanted to go back to the provinces (Gascon & Chiu, 2020) but also because some policies do not resonate with the marginalized and are non-responsive to the real challenges brought by the virus (Beltran, 2020). A closer look at some of these thematic policies would show how the government's national responses to COVID-19 impact traditional vulnerable sectors, such as daily wage earners, informal workers, PWDs, senior citizens, and the urban poor. A more critical eye would, however, see that, beyond the impact on the vulnerable sectors, the government has, through its very own policies, created a non-traditional vulnerable sector—locally stranded individuals (LSIs).

The Philippine Statistics Authority (2018) reported a decline in the Philippines' poverty rate from 23.3% in 2015 to 16.6% in 2018. With the sudden loss of income and other forms of insecurity that came out of community lockdowns and restrictions related to containing the pandemic, many poor households had to deal with poverty under more harsh circumstances (ADB, 2020). Recognizing this plight, the national government, under RA 11469 or the "Bayanihan to Heal as One" Act, provided subsidies through the Social Amelioration Program (SAP) to low-income families, amounting to PHP199.98 billion. Per Joint Memorandum Circular No. 1, s. 2020, this subsidy meant an allocation of between five PHP5,000 to PHP8,000 a month for 18 million families nationwide, spread out to two months during the quarantine period.

To help offset the economic impact of COVID-19 on low-income households, the distribution of SAP cannot have come at a better time. However, the lack of clear protocols and the fragmented, if not limited, availability of information on how the financial aid would be distributed to the target families, proved to be challenging both for the local government directed to manage the distribution and the families themselves who felt distressed waiting and lining up for help (Sta. Ana, 2020). The lack of protocol is aggravated by the absence of a national ID system, or an information system that could have made it easier for the local government to identify beneficiaries and roll out the aid distribution more efficiently.

Locally Stranded Individuals

The concept of unintended consequences generally refers to the unwelcome outcomes of organized actions or formal policies (de Zwart, 2015). In the Philippines'

fight against the COVID pandemic, one adverse outcome of some of its policies that stand out among lesser ones is the problem of locally stranded individuals (LSIs). LSIs are recognized by the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) as the unintended consequence of restrictions on the mobility of people because of policies meant to contain the virus from cross-border movement (DILG, 2020).

DILG Memorandum Circular No. 2020-087 classifies LSIs into workers, students, tourists, and others. Furthermore, it categorizes Returning Overseas Filipinos (ROFs) into (1) returning students, J1 visa holders/exchange visitors program beneficiaries, returning Filipino tourists, and participants of government-sponsored programs, and (2) dependents and accompanying foreign spouses. An important element of DILG Memorandum Circular No. 2020-087 is the creation of separate sub-task units to manage LSIs and ROFs.

Table 3
*Selected Policies on Locally Stranded Individuals (LSIs)
and Returning Overseas Filipinos (ROFs)*

Agency	Date	Policy
DILG	21 May 2020	DILG Memorandum Circular No. 2020-087
DOLE	25 March 2020	Department Order No. 211-20
Joint Agencies	June 2020	Hatid Probinsya

The National IATF guidelines allow local government units (LGUs) to define: (1) who may leave or enter the LGU; (2) how cash assistance or *ayuda* (help) will be distributed, to whom, and for how long; and (3) mobility in the LGUs that involve “quarantine passes” and policing movement during the various stages of lockdown. Based on these three features of the national government response to COVID-19, this section unpacks the effects on local communities, particularly in Metro Manila.

Early on, reports of LGUs outright refusing to accept OFWs into their hometowns emerged as early as March when the lockdowns began. Eventually, the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) declared that “LGUs that will deny entry to returning overseas Filipino workers (OFWs) who have been quarantined will be held liable” (Caliwan, 2020, para. 1). This followed reports of LGUs imposing “unnecessary” regulations or outright refusing properly documented OFWs that were cleared with proof of negative COVID-19 tests (Caliwan, 2020).

The burden of the RT PCR test on returning OFWs, or even LSIs, who have found themselves in LGUs other than their own during the lockdown, weighs heavily on lower-income returnees. The current “gold standard” of testing costs anywhere from PHP4,000 - PHP8,000 or USD82 - USD165 (San Juan, 2020). This amount is well above the minimum wage earner’s capability to pay. A family of four, for example, would require PHP16,000 - PHP32,000 for clearance to return to their hometown from high-risk areas, such as Metro Manila or Metro Cebu. As of this writing, other options, such as a locally developed RT PCR test priced at PHP1,320, were being considered by the Department of Health, pending the resolution of defective kits (San Juan, 2020). The dire situation of limited transportation and prohibitive requirements stretched out into months of waiting for LSIs as evidenced by the poorly coordinated

Hatid Tulong program that resulted in 8,400 LSIs densely packed into a Manila City stadium for days and in 48 recorded positive cases (Cepeda, 2020).

On 30 July 2020, the national government reneged on its plan to require LSIs to take a swab test before going to their home provinces, and instead transferred the requirement to LGUs accepting LSIs as well as private businesses. This was followed by a return to MECQ status in the National Capital Region (NCR), which once again halted public transportation in Metro Manila and other regions in the Philippines, further prolonging the travel of those stranded in big cities to their hometowns.

Ayuda: The Social Amelioration Program

As early as March 2020, the Department of Finance (DoF) promised cash assistance, as the prospect of a lockdown loomed over the country in an attempt to curb the spread of the virus. This promise was supported by the “Heal as One” Act, which also allowed for the use of underutilized funds towards the COVID-19 efforts.

LGUs were tasked to accept applications, identify beneficiaries, and distribute the cash subsidies to them. By the end of the two months, reports of undistributed subsidies prompted the then secretary of the DILG to fast-track the payout by the end of April (DILG, 2020). At the same time, independent efforts to assist families and individuals through donations were discouraged by the national government, which insisted that donation drives be reviewed by the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD). Before this, the Office of Civil Defense faced similar complaints about limiting direct donation efforts (Abad, 2020).

At the barangay level, more difficulties ensued, as the task of identifying qualified families to benefit from a limited number of earmarked subsidies fell on the shoulders of barangay leaders. The national government expected local government units to have a profile of people in their area (Talabong, 2020b).

Unmet expectations led to further chaos in highly urbanized areas, which compromised health and safety, as representatives of qualified families waited in long, haphazard lines to avail of the promised funds. With safety concerns, not just for recipients, those in the front line of relief efforts have also found themselves with inadequate protection from the virus—with 160 DSWD personnel in charge of distribution of cash assistance testing positive for COVID-19 in 2020 (Luci-Atienza, 2020).

Half a year deep into the crisis, many families are in the same situation, but without any cash subsidies left from the national government to reinforce the economic effects of the pandemic in a country known for the “world’s longest lockdown” thus far.

Community Quarantines

The term “community quarantine” is a recent addition to Philippine governance vocabulary—it is calibrated further by the prefixes “enhanced,” “general,” and “modified.” Ironically, the country was under community quarantine since March 2020, which points to a collective state of limited physical, social, and economic movement. An additional term, “hard lockdown,” was added to the quarantine-related lexicon to describe heavily policing areas (usually densely populated urban poor barangays) with a no entry-no exit policy for at least 48 hours. Even without the hard lockdown, Metro Manila and Metro Cebu endured months of life without public transportation, closed off non-essential businesses, and, for most, a daily painful

process of procuring essential goods, using a community quarantine pass issued by the local government to one person per family. People in urban areas, such as Metro Manila, and commuting workers from nearby provinces lived through months with these community passes, rather than living with more medically prudent measures, such as increased testing capacity.

The pandemic has prompted guidelines to ensure the safety of constituents at the local level for some, but it has increased precariousness for others. Limiting mobility, unsustainable dole-out programs and strict lockdown strategies without parallel community-based health interventions left workers in the informal sector, especially those living in the fringes of Metro Manila, urban poor communities, and OFWs adversely affected and disempowered by not just COVID-19-related risks, deep in economic uncertainty and physical jeopardy.

Migrant Workers

The nature of overseas Filipino workers' (OFWs) vulnerability has changed with the onset of the pandemic and raised fundamental questions on the capacity of state structures to provide adequate protection for them for a prolonged period. OFWs have found themselves at risk while at the frontlines in their host countries, and upon returning home after their contracts expire or termination of employment for COVID-related reasons.

The early responses to the COVID-19 pandemic were restrictions on international travelers. This is no easy task for a country like the Philippines, where approximately 10% of its population lives and works overseas. As the crisis hit OFW-rich countries and affected OFWs and returnees were making their way back into the country, a surprising trend emerged: local government units (LGUs) refused to accept their repatriates, some of whom were already suffering from intolerably long wait in makeshift quarantine facilities for COVID-19 results to be released.

On the other hand, those who waited deployment suffered similar fates. They are forced to languish in and around airports with neither the government nor the recruitment agency taking responsibility for their current condition.

The domestic service sector fared no better. Reports of "heavier workload and longer working hours" emerged as employers shifted to work-from-home arrangements and the number of household chores increased due to the entire household working and studying from home (Abao et al., 2020).

A later development involved an overseas deployment ban on Filipino healthcare professionals to assist the country's fight against the pandemic. Hard-pressed to work abroad due to the difficult working conditions and low wages and with the additional burden of COVID-19 risks, local healthcare workers have opted to take an often-chosen route: working abroad. The government's ban has been decried by nurses' groups, especially those who have been deployed before the ban.

In this pandemic, many OFWs still chose to stay at their place of work, despite the heavier workload and discrimination, rather than face unemployment and uncertainty back home (Abao et al., 2020). However, the longer the pandemic dragged on, and the scarcer the resources of employers were in host countries, the fewer OFWs were ensured of their basic rights, including health and safety. As the desire to return home grew, the prospects became dimmer as dwindling wages held back the workers from being able to go home (Redfern, 2020). In addition, the highly

restrictive international travel environment and the tedious process of returning to hometowns outside of the National Capitol Region (NCR) still challenged their way back home.

As the COVID-19 crisis deepens, the effects are yet to bottom out for a country that enjoyed USD 33.5 billion in remittances in 2019 (Rivas, 2020). Early projections expected one million OFW jobs lost by 2021 (Gonzales, 2020). These came with fissures reaching far down into areas, such as consumer spending, education, health, and local development. With each OFW supporting several family members, the expected effect of this loss is not just economically devastating but also socially precarious.

Analysis and Conclusion

A closer look at the COVID-19 experiences of neighboring countries in the region shows the need to balance a country's policy approach to pressing public health and economic concerns. Integral to the outcome of a pandemic response are the government's swift and decisive actions to mitigate virus transmission and its decision to adopt robust measures to test, trace, and quarantine possible cases of COVID-19, while also ensuring that social safety nets are provided to the people.

The Philippines' top-down, securitized, and state-imposed COVID-19 measures have managed to increase the risk of vulnerable groups through the following national directives: (1) the initial month-long strict lockdown that put heavy restrictions on the movement of people and cargoes, business operations, and general public transportation, even among medical frontliners; (2) international and domestic travel restrictions; (3) social distancing policies that have adversely affected workplace arrangements, business operations, and education policies; (4) different schemes of financial assistance for vulnerable groups; and (5) varying classifications of community quarantine based on low to high-risk assessment for a specific period.

At the local level, this was felt by: (1) the suspension of public transportation and inter-island mobility, which has resulted in the phenomenon of locally stranded individuals (LSIs); (2) the uneven, limited, and selective distribution of assistance through the social amelioration program; and (3) the implementation of the community quarantine, which posed difficulties in day-to-day living for families.

Further, the pandemic has also posed new risks for migrant workers. The OFWs' vulnerability increased, as seen in the various stages of the migration cycle: while working in the host state, due to the increased demands on their work brought about by changes caused by the pandemic, and when they return home and attempt to reintegrate into LGUs and home communities.

Returning to the framework, this article has shown that policies that sought to prevent the spread of COVID-19 early in the pandemic wrought graver consequences for many who were vulnerable or at risk. This became acutely obvious as national policies were translated to local responses with accompanying responsibilities for local government actors (Tables 4 and 5).

Table 4
Risk Factors

Policy Recommendations	Status	Date Implemented	Annotation
OFWs and locally stranded individuals	Limited mobility	IATF guidelines that allow LGUs to define assistance and mobility	“Hatid Probinsya” program Return to lower quarantine status level that allowed more freedom of movement
Informal workers in quarantine communities	Limited access to food and healthcare	Differences in restrictions between places of domicile and work	Community-based health interventions

Source. Beasley (2018).

Table 5
Effects of Localization of COVID-19-Related Responsibilities

Level of Governance	Recommendation
Local and regional	Rapid assessment tools and accessible and official communication will assist in early response decision making. This may include processes for mobile, itinerant, and informal sectors that may be more difficult to track. Measures to ensure the continued provision of basic services (transportation, education, and health) in prolonged emergencies
National	De-securitization of public health emergencies and flexibility with national guidelines may assist in appropriate responses during similar national emergencies.

Much is yet to be learned as the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic in the medium and long term (e.g., setbacks in the education sector and delayed economic growth) continue to emerge in the Philippine context. This may be where the value of (1) comparative studies with similarly situated Asian or developing countries; (2) long-term studies on effects on various sectors; and (3) piloting of successful programs may be further explored, to ensure that lessons learned are internalized and implemented for future possible events. Other areas relevant to the article that may require extensive research include public health management and policy review of existing healthcare systems. The former can focus on assessing the country’s health infrastructure in terms of its capability to address similar crises in the future. Meanwhile, the latter can offer a review of existing healthcare policies to areas of intervention to make it more affordable and accessible to vulnerable sectors.

References

- Abao, C., Lao, M. E. J., & Quintana, O. (2020). Political empowerment as protection: The way forward for Filipino domestic workers in a time of COVID-19. <https://arete.ateneo.edu/connect/political-empowerment-as-protection-the-way-forward-for-filipino-domestic-workers-in-the-time-of-covid-19>
- Abad, M. (2020). DSWD reminds public to get permits for donation drives. *Rappler*. <http://rappler.com/dswd-reminds-public-to-get-permits-for-donation-drives-require-permit>
- Al Jazeera (2020, August 6). *Philippine economy posts its biggest-ever quarterly plunge*. <https://www.aljazeera.com/economy/2020/8/6/philippine-economy-posts-its-biggest-ever-quarterly-plunge>
- Asian Development Bank (ADB). (2020). *Social Amelioration Program Guidelines*. <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/linked-documents/43407-017-sd-05.pdf>
- Beasley, R. (2018). Dissonance and decision-making mistakes in the age of risk. In *Fiascos in Public Policy and Foreign Policy* (pp. 141-158). Routledge.
- Beltran, M. (2020). The Philippines' pandemic response: A tragedy of errors. *The Diplomat*. <https://thediplomat.com/2020/05/the-philippines-pandemic-response-a-tragedy-of-errors/>
- Berse, K., Rañises, J. M., Florendo, G. B., Cariaga, M. D., Nera, A. D. P., Santiago, F. E., Nazal, M. A., & dela Torre, D. (2020). *Managing the COVID-19 pandemic in the Philippines: A policy sourcebook* (Vol. 1: National government). UP Resilience Institute.
- Berse, P. P. (2020). (Undisrupted) learning in the time of COVID-19. *Business World*. <https://www.bworldonline.com/undisrupted-learning-in-the-time-of-covid-19/>
- Cader, A. A., & Perera, L. (2011). *Understanding the impact of the economic crisis on child and maternal health among the poor: Opportunities for South Asia*. ADBI Working Paper 293. Asian Development Bank Institute. <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/156148/adbi-wp293.pdf>
- Caliwan, C. L. (2020). DILG to go after LGUs that reject returning OFWs. *Philippine Daily Inquirer*. <http://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1103947>
- Cepeda, M. (2020). HatidTulong Officials to Critics: 'Snapshots of crowd in Rizal stadium does not tell the entire story'. *Rappler*. <http://rappler.com/nation/hatid-tulong-officials-response-critics-snapshow-rizal-stadium-crowd/>
- Collantes, C. F. (2021). "Unforgotten" informal communities and the COVID-19 pandemic: Sitio San Roque under Metro Manila's lockdown. *International Journal of Human Rights in Healthcare*, 14(3), 279-292. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJHRH-09-2020-0073>
- De Vera, B. (2019). PH poverty rate seen falling below 20% starting 2020. <https://business.inquirer.net/281269/ph-poverty-rate-seen-falling-below-20-starting-2020>
- De Vera, B. (2020). Amid ECQ, 'record-high' unemployment rate of 17.7% posted in April. *Philippine Daily Inquirer*. <https://business.inquirer.net/299124/amid-ecq-record-high-unemployment-rate-of-17-7-posted-in-april>
- De Zwart, F. (2015). Unintended but not unanticipated consequences. *Theory and Society*, 44, 283-297. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11186-015-9247-6>
- Department of Interior and Local Government. (2020a). *DILG to LGUs: Complete distribution of SAP emergency subsidy by April 30*. <http://www.dilg.gov.ph/news/DILG-to-LGUs-Complete-distribution-of-SAP-emergency-subsidy-by-April-30/NC-2020-1113>.
- Department of Interior and Local Government. Memorandum Circular No. 2020-087. *Duties and Responsibilities of Local Government Officials, DILG Regional Directors and Field Officers, Philippine National Police, and others concerned on the Management of Returning Overseas Filipinos and Locally Stranded Individuals*. (2020b). https://www.dilg.gov.ph/PDF_File/issuances/memo_circulars/dilg-memocircular-2020521_a38badf755.pdf
- Executive Order No. 112. *Imposing an Enhanced Community Quarantine in High-Risk Geographic Areas of the Philippines and a General Community Quarantine in the Rest of the Country from 1 to 15 May 2020, Adopting the Omnibus Guidelines on the Implementation Thereof, and for Other Purposes*. (2020).
- Executive Order No. 114. *Institutionalizing the Balik Probinsya, Bagong Pag-Asa Program as a Pillar of Balanced Regional Development, Creating a Council Therefor, and for Other Purposes*. (2020).
- Gascon, M., & Chiu, P. D. M. (2020). DILG: 'Balik-Probinsya' not same as 'HatidProbinsya'. *Inquirer*. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1283703/dilg-balik-probinsya-not-same-as-hatid-probinsya>

- Gregorio, X. (2020). Movement of People in Luzon Restricted as Island Placed Under 'Enhanced' Community Quarantine. *CNN Philippines*. <https://www.cnnphilippines.com/news/2020/3/16/luzon-enhanced-community-quarantine-covid-19.html>
- Gonzales, C. (2020). 1 million OFWs may lose jobs due to COVID-19 pandemic – DOLE. *Inquirer*. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1286124/1-million-ofws-may-lose-jobs-due-to-covid-19-pandemic-dole>
- Hartley, K., Bales, S., & Bali, A. S. (2021). COVID-19 response in a unitary state: Emerging lessons from Vietnam. *Policy Practice*, 4(1), 152-168. https://doi.org/10.1080/25741292_2021.1877923
- Hecita, I. J., Torneo, A., Panelo, D., & Miranda, K. (2023). Securitisation of the pandemic response in the Philippines. *Regional Studies Policy Impact Books*, 5(1), 89-109, <https://doi.org/10.1080/2578711X.2023.2196215>
- IATF Resolution No. 1, s. 2020. *Recommendations for the Management of Novel Coronavirus Situation*. (2020).
- IATF Resolution No. 4, s. 2020. *Implementing the Expanded Travel Ban for the Management of the 2019 Novel Coronavirus Acute Respiratory Disease Situation, Amending for the Purpose Resolution No. 2*. (2020).
- IATF Resolution No. 10, s. 2020. *Recommendations for the Management of the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Situation*. (2020).
- IATF Resolution No. 12, s. 2020. *Recommendations for the Management of the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Situation*. (2020).
- IATF Resolution No. 14, s. 2020. *Resolutions Relative to the Management of the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Situation*. (2020).
- IATF Resolution No. 15, s. 2020. *Resolutions Relative to the Management of the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Situation*. (2020).
- Luci-Atienza, C. (2020). *DSWD Records 160 cases of COVID 19*. Manila Bulletin. <https://mb.com.ph/2020/08/15/dswd-records-160-cases-of-covid-19/>
- Merez, A. (2020). Duterte places Philippines under state of calamity until September 2021. *ABS-CBN News*. <https://news.abs-cbn.com/news/09/18/20/philippines-to-remain-under-state-of-calamity-until-september-2021>
- Molenaar, J., & Van Praag, L. (2022). Migrants as 'vulnerable groups' in the COVID-19 pandemic: A critical discourse analysis of a taken-for-granted label in academic literature. *SSM-Qualitative Research in Health*, 2, 1-9.
- Montemayor, M. T. (2020). Task Force Imposes Social Distancing Measures vs. COVID-19. Philippine News Agency. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1096064>
- National Economic and Development Authority. (2017). Chapter 11: Reducing vulnerability of individuals and families. In *Philippine Development Plan 2017-2022*. <https://pdp.neda.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/Chapter-11.pdf>
- Philippine Statistics Authority (2020). *Employment rate in January 2020 is estimated at 94.7 percent*. <https://psa.gov.ph/content/employment-rate-january-2020-estimated-947-percent>
- Presidential Proclamation No. 922, s. 2020. *Declaring a State of Public Health Emergency Throughout the Philippines*. (2020).
- Presidential Proclamation No. 929, s. 2020. *Declaring a State of Calamity Throughout the Philippines due to Corona Virus Disease 2019*. (2020).
- Redfern, C. (2020). 'I want to go home': Filipina domestic workers face exploitative conditions. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2021/jan/27/domestic-workers-philippines-coronavirus-conditions>
- Regan, H. (2020, June 12). Stranded Filipino woman Michelle Silvertino died after waiting days for a bus home during lockdown. *CNN*. <https://edition.cnn.com/2020/06/12/asia/philippines-stranded-worker-death-intl-hnk-scli/index.html>
- Republic Act 11469. *Bayanihan to Heal as One Act*. (2020).
- Republic Act 11494. *Bayanihan to Recover as One Act*. (2020).
- Rivas, R. (2020). OFW remittances hit record high of \$33.5 billion in 2019. *Rappler*. <https://www.rappler.com/business/252043-overseas-filipino-workers-remittances-2019/>
- Rukmana, D. (2014). Vulnerable Populations. In Michalos, A.C. (ed.), *Encyclopedia of Quality of Life and Well-Being Research*. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-0753-5_3184

- San Juan, R. (2020). Senators to DOH: Use cheaper Filipino-made COVID 19 test kits instead of imported brands. *Philippine Star*. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2020/07/18/2028907/senators-doh-use-cheaper-filipino-made-covid-19-test-kits-instead-imported-brands/amp/>
- Social Weather Stations (2019). Fourth Quarter 2019 Social Weather Survey: Pres. Duterte's Net Satisfaction at New Record "Excellent" +72. <https://www.sws.org.ph/swsmain/artcldisppage/?artcsyscode=ART-20200121185102>
- Sta. Ana III, F.S. (2020). COVID-19 social amelioration issues. *Business World*. <https://www.bworldonline.com/covid-19-social-amelioration-issues/>
- Talabong, R. (2020a). Duterte chaos leaves barangay officials 'helpless' amid lockdowns. *Rappler*. <http://rappler.com/newsbreak/in-depth/duterte-chaose-leaves-barangay-officials-helpless-coronavirus-lockdown>
- Talabong, R. (2020b). Walang malapitan: Stranded 'probinsyanos' feel abandoned by Duterte gov't. *Rappler*. <https://www.rappler.com/newsbreak/in-depth/262143-stranded-probinsyanos-feel-abandoned-duterte-government-coronavirus-pandemic/>
- United Nations Vietnam (2020). *UN assessment of the social and economic impact of COVID-19 in Vietnam*. <https://vietnam.un.org/en/95127-un-assessment-social-and-economic-impact-covid-19-viet-nam>
- World Bank (2019). *Philippines Economic Update 2019*. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/philippines/publication/philippines-economic-update-october-2019-edition>

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